

THE EFFECT OF AQUEOUS EXTRACT OF *Hibiscus Sabdariffa L.* ON THE ACTIVITY OF ALKALINE PHOSPHATASE AND URIC ACID IN THE LIVER OF *Rattus novergicus*.

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ABSTRACT

The effect of aqueous extract of *Hibiscus sabdariffa L.* on the activity of alkaline phosphatase and uric acid in the liver of *Rattus novergicus* was studied in this research. The result from this study revealed that the activities of alkaline phosphatase in the serum slightly increased (18.00 ± 3.39) when compared with that of the control (16.37 ± 3.50) at ($P < 0.05$) (Table. 1), though this was not statistically significant but there was a statistically significant increase in the serum uric acid (0.17 ± 0.21) when compared with the control (0.016 ± 0.02) at $P < 0.05$ (Table 1). The result from the investigation of liver alkaline phosphatase, showed that there was a slight increase (4.31 ± 3.39) when compared with that of the control (3.84 ± 2.02) at $P < 0.05$ (Table.2). However, liver uric acid level of the test group was increased (0.50 ± 0.15) when compared with the control (0.27 ± 0.09) (Table 2). The results of the study suggest that zobo drink at the level of administration (140ml 3 times a day), has no serious health implication on the liver and that *Hibiscus Sabdariffa L.* may be very rich in purine substances because, any food/drink rich in purines, when consumed, increases the uric acid level in serum which is not regarded as health threat. If the increase in liver ALP was statistically significant, then one would have queried that the consumption of ZOBO drink may cause problem. But as it is from this study, the researcher is of the view that consumption of zobo drink is healthy.

KEYWORDS: Zobo drink, *Hibiscus Sabdariffa L.*, alkaline phosphatase, uric acid, liver and *Rattus novergicus*.

INTRODUCTION:

Hibiscus Sabdariffa Linn. is the botanical name of a plant known as Roselle. It is a shrub belonging to the family *Malvaceae*; Its common name include Roselle and Jamaican Sorrel; it is though, of native of Asia or tropical Africa. The plant is widely grown in tropics like Indian, Africa, Brazil and Phillipines and in Nigeria it is commonly grown and used as port herb or soup in the northern part of the country (Dahiruet *et al.*, 2003). *Hibiscus Sabdariffa L.* has been discovered to lower high blood pressure. Its leaves and fruits are found in many remedies for viral hepatitis, constipation and round worm infestation. However, it is lightly acidic with a pH of about 3.5 which reduces with time. *Hibiscus Sabdariffa L.* is a medicinal herb used in folk medicine in the treatment of hypertension (Wanget *et al.*, 2000; Odigie *et al.*, 2003). The plant is about 3-5m tall and has a deep penetrating taproot with a smooth cylindrical, typically dark green to red stem. The chemical constituent of the flower include the flavonoid, gossypetin and subdaretine (Vilasineet *et al.*, 2005).

Tea of calyces showed 11.2% reduction in the blood pressure systolic and 10.75% decrease in the diastolic pressure. Effectiveness and tolerability of a standardized extract was studied in patients with mild to moderate hypertension which revealed a reduction in systolic and diastolic blood pressure by more than 10% (Herrera *et al.*, 2004). Aqueous ethanol extract of the calyx showed a significant decrease in the level of lipid peroxidation in carbon tetrachloride induced liver damage (Dahiru *et al.*, 2003). Research has also shown that anthocyanins of this plant may be used to inhibit low density lipoprotein (LDL) oxidation serving as a chemopreventive agent and as a cancer chemopreventive agent against tumour promotion (Tseng *et al.*, 1998).

The liver fraction is believed to be involved in the transport process and that the primary importance of measuring alkaline phosphatase is to check the possibility of bone or liver disease since the mucosal cells that line the bile system of the liver are the source of alkaline phosphatase, the free flow of bile through the liver and down into the biliary tract and gall bladder are responsible for maintaining the proper level of this enzyme in the blood. When the liver, bile ducts or gall bladder system are not functioning properly or are blocked, this enzyme is not excreted through the bile hence alkaline phosphatase is released into the blood stream (Jeroh *et al.*, 2012).

Uric acid is a heterocyclic compound of carbon, nitrogen, oxygen and hydrogen with the formula $C_5H_4N_4O_3$. Uric acid is produced by Xanthine oxidase from xanthine and hypoxanthine, which in turn are produced from purine. Uric acid is more toxic to tissues than either xanthine or hypoxanthine and is released in hypoxic condition. In humans and higher primates, uric acid is the final oxidation (breakdown) product of purine metabolism and is excreted in urine. Elevated serum uric acid can result from high intake of purine rich foods and impaired excretion by the kidneys (Heinig and Johnson, 2006).

In Nigeria, a red coloured soft drink which is a hot-water extract of the red flower of the *Hibiscus sabdariffa* is chilled and marketed as 'ZOBO DRINK'

This study investigated the effect of aqueous extract of *Hibiscus sabdariffa L.* on the activity of alkaline phosphatase and uric acid in the liver of *Rattus norvegicus* (Wistar rat).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Animal care ethics:

Ten *Rattus norvegicus* (Wistar rats) of both sexes with average weight of 231g were randomly assigned into two groups A and B. Group A served as control while group B served as the treatment group. The rats were obtained and maintained in the Animal Holdings of the department of Anatomy, School of Basic Medical Sciences, University of Benin. The animals were fed with grower's mash obtained from Top feed limited, Sapele, Delta State, the distilled water was obtained from the department of Anatomy, University of Benin, while the *hibiscus Sabdariffa L.* was obtained from Oba market in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria.

Zobo administration:

Rattus norvegicus in the control groups A were given 140ml of water while the experimental group B was given 140ml of freshly prepared zobo drink liberally, on a daily basis for thirty one days. This was repeated thrice daily. *R. norvegicus* were then sacrificed by cervical dislocation on the thirty-second day of the experiment. 5ml of blood was collected and put in a test tube and spun in a centrifuge for 15mins to obtain the serum and then the liver was quickly obtained and placed in ice to avoid enzyme denaturation. 0.5g of the obtained liver was homogenated with 10% normal saline for biochemical assay after the homogenates were centrifuged at high speed to separate the components.

Biochemical Assay:

The measurement of enzyme activity and uric acid were done using the spectrophotometer.

Statistical Analysis:

The results were expressed as mean±SD. The student t-test was used for the evaluation of statistical significance. The results were judged significant if $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

In Nigeria, a red coloured soft drink which is a hot-water extract of the red flower of the *Hibiscus sabdariffa* is chilled and marketed as 'ZOBO DRINK'

Hibiscus sabdariffa L. has been discovered to lower high blood pressure. Its leaves and fruits are found in many remedies for viral hepatitis, constipation and round worm infestation. However, it is lightly acidic with a pH of about 3.5 which reduces with time.

Table 1: The activities of alkaline phosphatase (ALP) and uric acid in serum of *Rattus norvegicus*.

Parameters	Control (A)	Treatment (B)
ALP (u/l)	16.37±3.50	18.00±3.39*
Uric acid(mMol/l)	0.016±0.0	20.17±0.21*

Table 2: The activities of alkaline phosphatase (ALP) and uric acid in the liver of *rattusnovergicus*

Parameters	Control (A)	Treatment (B)
ALP (u/l)	3.84±2.02	4.31±3.39
Uric acid (mMol/l)	0.27±0.09	0.50±0.15*

Values are mean±SD, n=5.

* represent significant differences of test groups in comparison with respective controls; at (P<0.05).

The result from this study revealed that the activities of alkaline phosphatase in the serum slightly increased (18.00±3.39) when compared with that of the control (16.37±3.50) at (P<0.05) (Table. 1), though this was not statistically significant but there was a statistically significant increase in the serum uric acid (0.17±0.21) when compared with the control (0.016±0.02) at P<0.05 (Table 1). The implication of this result is that *Hibiscus sabdariffa.L.* may be very rich in purine substances because, any food food/drink rich in purines when consumed increases the level of uric acid level in serum which is not regarded as health threat unless some associated disease may have been inherent. This is in line with Heinig and Johnson, 2006).

The result from the investigation of liver alkaline phosphatase, showed that there was a slight increase (4.31±3.39) when compared with that of the control (3.84±2.02) at P<0.05 (Table.2). The implication of this study is that the zobo drink at the level of administration has no serious health implication in the liver. However, liver uric acid level of the test group was increased (0.50±0.15) when compared with the control (0.27±0.09) (Table 2). This was statistically significant at (P<0.05). The implication of this result is that at the level of administration (140ml 3 times a day), the liver is healthy and carrying out its detoxification reaction via catabolism of purine would have led to increased uric acid level since *Hibiscus sabdariffa.L.* may be rich in purines. Researches have also shown that it is rich in ascorbic acid (Mohammed *et al.*, 2007). If the increase in liver ALP was statistically significant, then one would have queried that the consumption of ZOBO drink may cause problem. But as it is from this study, the researcher is of the view that consumption of 'ZOBO' drink at the 'LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATION' in this study is healthy.

CONCLUSION

This research has shown that ZOBO drink at the LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATION (140ml 3 times a day), has no serious health implication on the liver. It is important to note that *Hibiscus sabdariffa.L* may be very rich in purine substances. It has also been observed that any food food/drink rich in purines, when consumed, increases the uric acid level in serum which is not regarded as health threat. If the increase in liver ALP was statistically significant, then one would have queried that the consumption of ZOBO drink may cause problem. But as it is from this study, the researcher is of the view that consumption of ZOBO drink at the LEVEL OF ADMINISTRATION in this study is healthy.

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